

EZ-AR: An accessible AR application for multiple model visualization and real-time tracking in healthcare settings.

- Supplementary Document -

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1. Introduction

This document supplements the article "*EZ-AR: An accessible AR application for multiple model visualization and real-time tracking in healthcare settings*," which presents a novel framework designed to bring augmented reality closer to non-expert users by enabling them to deploy their own virtual 3D models on Microsoft HoloLens 2 without programming. It is designed for users without prior AR development experience, supporting the creation of customized AR applications through an intuitive, code-free workflow. Practical recommendations are also provided regarding model optimization, file size limitations, and Google Drive accessibility requirements.

The following sections provide detailed guidance on using the EZ-AR setup module, developed for 3D Slicer, as well as the AR application for Microsoft HoloLens 2 (*EZ-AR*).

2. EZ-AR setup: The 3D Slicer module

This section describes each of the four main components of the 3D Slicer module: *Initialization*, *Positioning*, *Customize Models Info and Saving*, and *Save Configuration File*; and explains how to properly prepare the necessary files for successful deployment and visualization of the 3D virtual models within the Microsoft HoloLens 2 environment.

2.1. Initialization

This block is divided into two subsections: AR Marker and 3D Models. Figure 1 shows a screenshot of this section in 3D Slicer.

Figure 1. “Initialization” section of EZ-AR setup module in 3D Slicer.

- AR marker: One of the main objectives of this study is to propose and compare two alternative tracking methods for Microsoft HoloLens 2. In this subsection, users are asked to choose which tracking method they prefer to use: Vuforia or QR tracking. The application supports both options, and the decision is entirely up to the user, based on personal preferences or available resources. To assist in selecting the most suitable option, the main manuscript includes a series of experiments that evaluate and compare the overall system accuracy using each tracking method.
- 3D models: Once the reference marker has been defined, the next step allows users to select the virtual models to be visualized in the AR application from the local storage of their PC. The system supports the import of up to eight models. To optimize performance on the headset, it is recommended to decimate the models as much as possible (without compromising surface resolution). A maximum file size of 10 MB per model is recommended.

2.2. Positioning

After selecting the models of interest, this section provides a set of sliders that allow users to translate and rotate all models along the three main axes with respect to the AR reference marker, treating them as a single group (Figure 2). An additional slider is also provided to scale all models uniformly, offering maximum flexibility in adjusting their appearance relative to the selected AR reference marker.

The image shows a software interface for positioning models. It is organized into sections: 'POSITIONING', 'Scale', 'Traslation', and 'Rotation'. The 'Scale' section has a slider labeled '[%]' set to 100.00. The 'Traslation' section has three sliders for LR, PA, and IS, all set to 0.00. The 'Rotation' section also has three sliders for LR, PA, and IS, all set to 0.00. At the bottom, there are two buttons: 'Save this position' and 'Reset position'.

Figure 2. “Positioning” section of EZ-AR setup module in 3D Slicer.

2.3. Customize models info and saving

In this section, the user is required to provide the desired display name and color for each model in the AR application (Figure 3), as well as an output folder in the local storage of the user’s computer.

In that folder, the current 3D Slicer scene will be saved in .mrb format for future reference. The transformation applied to the models during the *Positioning* step will also be saved as a file named “*fromModelToMarkerTransform.h5*”. Finally, all models will be hardened and exported in .obj format—compatible with Microsoft HoloLens 2—using the Model names established by the user.

The image shows a software interface for customizing model information and saving. It has a title bar 'CUSTOMIZE MODELS INFO and SAVING'. Below it are four rows of input fields: 'Select model:' with a dropdown menu showing 'Skull_model'; 'Model name:' with a text box containing 'Skull'; 'Select color:' with a color picker showing '#ffffc4'; and 'Save Location:' with a folder icon and a text box containing 'SaveTheseModels'. At the bottom, there is a 'Save data' button.

Figure 3. “Customize models info and saving” section of EZ-AR setup module in 3D Slicer.

2.4. Save Configuration file

To finish, the user must decide whether to upload the information to Google Drive (requires an internet connection) for automatic retrieval by the headset, or to transfer the models manually to the glasses (locally, offline) (Figure 4). If the second option is selected, the user simply has to click on “*Save configuration file*” to automatically generate a JSON file that summarizes all user-defined settings, including model names, colors (in hexadecimal format), and the selected tracking method.

If the user prefers Google Drive, they must upload all models to Drive, set their visibility to “*Anyone with the link*”, and paste the corresponding URLs into the designated boxes. Subsequently, the user must also click on “*Save configuration file*”. In this case, the generated JSON file will also contain the URLs adapted for automatic download.

Finally, the configuration file must also be uploaded to the Google Drive folder with its sharing settings set to “*Anyone with the link*” to ensure accessibility from the AR headset. An example of the configuration file is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. “*Save Configuration File*” section of EZ-AR setup module in 3D Slicer.

```
{
  "tracking_option": "Vuforia",
  "model1_url": "https://drive.google.com/uc?export=download&id=[EarModelID]",
  "model1_name": "Ear",
  "model1_material_color": "#38bce0",
  "model2_url": "https://drive.google.com/uc?export=download&id=[SkullModelID]",
  "model2_name": "Skull",
  "model2_material_color": "#feffd8",
  "model3_url": "https://drive.google.com/uc?export=download&id=[SplintModelID]",
  "model3_name": "Splint",
  "model3_material_color": "#e30c10",
  "model4_url": "",
  "model4_name": "",
  "model4_material_color": "",
  "model5_url": "",
  "model5_name": "",
  "model5_material_color": "",
  "model6_url": "",
  "model6_name": "",
  "model6_material_color": "",
  "model7_url": "",
  "model7_name": "",
  "model7_material_color": "",
  "model8_url": "",
  "model8_name": "",
  "model8_material_color": ""
}
```

Figure 5. Example of configuration file (“*config_file.json*”) generated by the 3D Slicer module with all necessary information for 3D virtual model download and display in Microsoft HoloLens 2.

3. EZ-AR: The AR application for Microsoft HoloLens 2

Upon launch, the application initiates a sequential validation process to ensure that all required components are correctly configured. The first step is to verify access to the configuration file generated in 3D Slicer. If the file cannot be located, a warning message prompts the user to paste the sharing link from Google Drive into the file named *Configuration file url.txt*. To do that, users must open the Windows Device Portal for Microsoft HoloLens 2 from a computer connected to the same Wi-Fi network. After logging in with the headset's credentials, users should navigate to: *System > File Explorer > Local App Data > EZ-AR > LocalState > Configuration file url.txt*. Once the link is detected, the application verifies that it is correctly formatted and publicly accessible before initiating the download. Alternatively, to comply with strict data privacy protocols, users can bypass the cloud entirely and transfer the configuration file (as well as the 3D models) directly to the headset's local storage via the Windows Device Portal. Afterward, the file is parsed to determine which tracking system should be used. The corresponding initialization routine is then executed based on the selected method. If Vuforia is chosen, an additional warning panel prompts the user to enter a valid Vuforia license key.

3.1. User interface

After initialization, a generic user interface is displayed half a meter in front of the user (Figure 6A). This interface can be repositioned within the environment. The UI includes eight toggle buttons, each corresponding to a distinct virtual 3D model.

Figure 6. User interface of the EZ-AR application in Microsoft HoloLens 2. (A) Unconfigured control panel displayed before any 3D virtual models are loaded. (B) Control panel adjusted after loading four personalized 3D virtual models.

The *Load Models* button must always be pressed first, initializing the application according to the user-defined parameters. When clicked, it downloads the virtual 3D models from Google Drive using the direct download URLs provided in the configuration file. The downloaded models are stored in the headset's local storage, eliminating the need for an internet connection in future sessions. This means that connectivity is only required during the initial setup. This step is bypassed if the models were originally passed to the headset via the Windows Device Portal. Once the loading process is complete, tracking of the desired AR reference marker begins. The 3D virtual models are automatically instantiated in their corresponding positions in the real space with their assigned colors. The model names specified in the configuration file are mapped, in order, to the corresponding toggle buttons. If fewer than eight models are defined, the unused buttons are removed, and the interface layout is adjusted to evenly fill the designated space (Figure 6B).

On the right side of the control panel, a set of interactive elements allows users to apply visualization adjustments to individual models by selecting the corresponding toggle button beforehand. The *All Models* button applies these settings to all models simultaneously. The options are:

- The *Visibility* toggle button lets users show or hide a selected model.
- The *Opacity* slider controls the transparency of the models.
- The *Manipulation* toggle switch converts the virtual 3D models into fully interactive objects that can be grabbed, translated, rotated, and scaled using hand gestures. When this option is turned off, the models remain anchored and move only with respect to the AR reference marker.

The *Manipulation* functionality may be particularly useful in surgical contexts. For example, to temporarily enlarge anatomical structures that are difficult to interpret. Models can be restored to their original pose relative to the AR reference marker at any time by pressing the *Reset Pose* button. The application also allows users to toggle the headset's tracking capability, enabling or disabling detection of the AR reference marker as needed. Finally, the *Clear Memory* button erases all downloaded content from the device's local storage. This feature is intended to facilitate loading a new configuration file, for instance, when switching to data from another patient.